

FTIR, ^1H NMR, mass spectral, XRD and thermal characterization studies of Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} complexes of glipizide : An oral antidiabetic drug

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Abstract : The present paper deals with the study of sulphonylurea glipizide (GLP) drug in order to give a thought concerning its coordinating potentiality towards some inner transition metals. Metal complexes of glipizide drug is prepared and characterized based on analytical data, molar conductance, IR, ^1H NMR, mass spectrometry, X-ray diffraction and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) studies. From the analytical data, the complexes are proposed to have general formulae $(\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{S})_2\text{Nd}(\text{OH}_2)_4$ and $(\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{S})_2\text{Sm}(\text{OH}_2)_4$. Low values of molar conductance indicate that complexes have non ionic nature. The conductometric titration using monovariation method reveal that complexes are L_2M type which is further confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation as modified by Turner and Anderson. Geometry of complexes are assigned to be hexagonal in which ligand molecules lie horizontally joining the central metal atom and four water molecules attached vertically and horizontally with the metal, supported by IR, ^1H NMR and mass studies. Powder X-ray diffraction data have been used to calculate particle size, porosity, volume of unit cell and density of synthesized complexes. The thermal decomposition of complexes is studied using thermogravimetric (TGA) techniques. The kinetic parameters such as, energy of activation (E_a), enthalpy (ΔH), entropy (ΔS) and free energy change (ΔG) of the complexes is evaluated by employing the Freeman-Carroll and Sharp-Wentworth methods and the relative thermal stability of the complexes are discussed.

Keywords : Glipizide, antidiabetic drug, metal complexes, spectroscopy, XRD, TGA.

Introduction

The term *diabetes mellitus* describes a metabolic disorder of multiple etiologies characterized by chronic hyperglycemia with disturbances of carbohydrate, fat and protein metabolism resulting from defects in insulin secretion, insulin action or both¹. Currently *diabetic mellitus* is a great threat to the world community with more than 100 million persons suffering from diabetes, which includes India also². Tolbutamide and chlorpropamide were the first widely used members of this group. Since then, about 12000 sulphonylureas have been tested^{3,4}. The first generation sulphonylureas are still in use, but are less effective than the more recently introduced second generation drugs like gliclazide, glimepiride, glibenclamide and glipizide⁵. An important difference between the older and newer sulphonylureas is a higher specific binding of the latter to pancreatic β -cells. Therefore, the newer

sulphonylureas, such as glipizide, are more active⁶ (Scheme 1). It is white to almost white crystalline odourless powder and insoluble in water, alcohol and readily soluble in dimethylformamide (DMF). Its melting range is 208–209 °C. Glipizide is one of the most commonly prescribed

Scheme 1. Structure of Glipizide drug.

drugs for treatment of type 2 *diabetes mellitus*⁷. Its main features are swift and short action with a very high selectivity^{8,9}. It is about 100 times more potent than tolbutamide in evoking pancreatic secretion of insulin¹⁰. Major

effect of glipizide is to enhance insulin availability following meals, whilst it has little influence on nocturnal glucose control¹¹. The study of chemistry and chemical reaction of co-ordination compound helps in establishing structure activities relationship. It has been reported that in biological activity metal complexes are more potent and less toxic as compared to the free ligand¹²⁻¹⁵. Recently, metals in medicine have been recognized internationally as an important area for research and much attention has been given to the use of sulphonylureas with inner transition metals because of their high complexing nature¹⁶⁻¹⁸. In this account, we have undertaken the neodymium trioxide (Nd₂O₃) and samarium trioxide (Sm₂O₃) metal complexes of glipizide drug for study. The metal complexes were characterised by using different physico-chemical methods like elemental analyses (C, H, N, S and metal content), IR, ¹H NMR, mass spectrometry, X-ray diffraction and TGA technique.

Experimental

Ligand-metal ratio :

(a) To find out the ligand metal ratio, initially conductometric titration using monovariation method were carried out at 27 ± 1 °C and 0.005 M solution of glipizide drug was prepared in DMF (dimethylformamide). Similarly, solution of Nd₂O₃ and Sm₂O₃ were prepared in the ethanol of 0.01 M concentration. 20 ml of ligand was diluted to 200 ml with the same solvent. The ligand was titrated conductometrically against metal salt solution taken in burette using fraction of 1 ml. Conductance was recorded after each addition with proper stirring. Results were plotted in the form of graph between corrected conductance and volume of metal salt added. From the equivalence point in the graph, ratio between ligand and metal were noted to be 2 : 1 (L₂ : M).

(b) Formation of these complexes in 2 : 1 (L₂ : M) ratio was also confirmed by Job's method¹⁹ of continuous variation as modified by Turner and Anderson²⁰, using conductance as index property Fig. 1(a)-(b) and Fig. 2(a)-(b) from these values the stability constant (log *k*) and free energy change (ΔF), were also calculated by using formula²¹⁻²⁴;

$$k = \frac{x}{(a_2-x)(b_2-2x)^2} = \frac{x}{(a_2-x)(b_2-2x)^2}$$

Material and method :

All chemicals used were of the analytical grade (AR) and of highest purity available. They include pure sample of glipizide received as a gift from M/s Zim Laboratories Limited, Kalmeshwar, Maharashtra, India. The metal salt of Nd₂O₃ and Sm₂O₃ obtained from Hi media Laboratory, Mumbai, India. Organic solvents used included absolute ethanol and DMF. De-ionised water was generally used in all synthesis.

Synthesis of metal complex :

A weighed quantity of "Glipizide" (2 mol) was dissolved separately in minimum quantity of DMF. The solution of Nd and Sm were prepared by dissolving separately in the ethanol. Ligand solution was added slowly with stirring into the solution of metallic salt at room temperature; maintain the pH between 6.0 to 6.5 by adding dilute NaOH solution. On refluxing the mixture for 3-4 h at 70 °C and on cooling, off white and light yellow crystals were collected by filtration, washed several times with DMF and ethanol finally dried in vacuum and weighed.

Instrumentation :

Molar conductance of complexes was measured by using Systronics Digital Conductivity meter. Melting point was determined by Perkin-Elmer Model melting point apparatus and is uncorrected. The elemental analysis of the isolated complexes was carried out by using Coleman Analyzer Model at the Departmental Micro Analytical Laboratory, CDRI, Lucknow, India. IR spectra of ligand and complexes were recorded with Perkin-Elmer Model 577 Spectrophotometer in the wave range of 4000-450 cm⁻¹ as KBr pellets CDRI, Lucknow, India. ¹H NMR spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded on a Bruker DRX-300 spectrophotometer and DMSO-*d*₆ was used as solvent CDRI, Lucknow, India. The ESI-MS Mass Spectra for GLP-Nd and GLP-Sm complexes were performed on Waters UPLC-TQD Mass Spectrometer. The given samples were subjected as such in front of DART source. Dry helium was used with 4LPM flow rate for ionization at 350 °C. The orifice set at 28 V and spectra were collected and print outs are averaged spectra of 6-8 scan at CDRI, Lucknow, India which provides information about the complexes by examining the fragmentation pattern and total mass of the complexes. X-Ray dif-

Fig. 1. Glipizide with Nd_2O_3 (modified Job's method) : (A) Job's curve, (B) modified Job's curve.

Fig. 2. Glipizide with Sm_2O_3 (modified Job's method) : (A) Job's curve, (B) modified Job's curve.

fraction studies was carried out by X-ray diffractometer model with 45 kV rotating anode and $\text{CuK}\alpha$ ($1 \text{ W} = 1.54060 \text{ \AA}$) radiation at Punjab University, Chandigarh, India. The sample was scanned in the range 10.0084 to 79.9804 (2θ) powder data were indexes using computer software (FPSUIT V2.0). The thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) were carried out in dynamic nitrogen atmosphere (20 ml min^{-1}) with a heating rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ using Shimadzu TGA-50H Thermal Analyzer at IIT Bombay, India.

Results and discussion

The synthesized complexes are off white and light yellow being soluble in DMSO and insoluble in water, ethanol etc. Analytical data and conductometric studies suggest 2 : 1 (L : M) ratio. Structures for the complexes are shown in Scheme 2(a)-(b).

Composition of metal complexes :

The isolated solid complexes of neodymium and samarium metal ions with the GLP ligand is subjected to elemental analyses (C, H, N, S and metal content) and

molar conductance. The results of physical and analytical data are given in Table 1.

IR spectral studies :

The IR data of the spectra of GLP ligand and its complexes is listed in Table 2²⁵⁻³⁰. The coordination sites that may be involved in chelation as shown in Fig. 3(a)-(c). The tautomeric equilibrium depends on the degree of conjugation, nature and position of the substituents, polarity of the solvent etc.

^1H NMR studies :

This technique gives us information about the number and types of atoms in molecule and also gave useful information regarding the environment of protons present in the complex. Fig. 4(a)-(c) shows the ^1H NMR spectra for GLP ligand and its complexes. Assignment of "Glipizide"-neodymium complex, molecular formula ($\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{S}$) $_2\text{Nd}(\text{OH}_2)_4$ (Mol. wt. = 1107.34), δ 8.98–9.03 (t, 1H-pyrazine ring), 8.60 (s, 1H-pyrazine ring), 7.76–7.81 (d, 1H-benzene ring), 7.42–7.45 (d, 1H-benzene ring), 6.30–6.33 (d, 1H-benzene ring), 3.54–3.60

Scheme 2(a). Structure of GLP-Nd complex.

Scheme 2(b). Structure of GLP-Sm complex.

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of Nd and Sm complexes

Complexes	Color (Yield %)	M.p. (°C)	Elemental analysis (%) :						Λ_m ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$)	log <i>K</i> (L/mole)	ΔF (kcal/mole)
			Calcd. (Found)				Metal	H ₂ O			
$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{27}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{S}$	White	208	56.55 (56.45)	6.05 (6.01)	15.71 (15.65)	7.18 (7.13)	–	–	–	–	–
$(\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{S})_2\text{Nd}(\text{OH}_2)_4$	Off white (51)	220	45.51 (45.44)	4.69 (5.46)	12.64 (12.52)	5.77 (5.70)	13.02 (12.96)	6.50 (6.61)	26.15	11.57	-15.85
$(\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{S})_2\text{Sm}(\text{OH}_2)_4$	Light yellow (56)	217	45.27 (45.18)	4.67 (4.62)	12.57 (12.48)	5.74 (5.60)	13.47 (13.42)	6.46 (6.43)	28.32	11.68	-16.08

(1H (NHCO)), 3.33–3.60 (s, 1H (NHSO₂)), 3.25–3.28 (t, 4H (-CH₂-CH₂ attached with benzene)), 2.50–2.55 (s, (CH₃ attached with pyrazine ring)), 2.50 (s, residual solvent DMSO-*d*₆), 1.02–1.64 (m, cyclohexane ring) respectively.

Assignment of “Glipizide”-samarium complex, molecular formula $(\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{S})_2\text{Sm}(\text{OH}_2)_4$ (Mol. wt. = 1113.15), δ 8.93–8.98 (t, 1H-pyrazine ring), 7.74–7.77 (d, 1H-benzene ring), 7.43–7.48 (d, 1H-benzene ring), 6.28–6.31 (d, 1H-benzene ring), 3.53–3.61 (1H (NHCO)), 3.31 (s, 1H (NHSO₂)), 3.24 (t, 4H (-CH₂-CH₂ attached with benzene)), 2.47–2.55 (s, (CH₃ attached with pyrazine ring)), 2.50 (s, residual solvent DMSO-*d*₆), 1.05–1.58 (m, cyclohexane ring) respectively. The structure for the complexes is also supported by various authors^{31–34}.

Mass spectral studies :

Mass spectra represent the intensities of signals at various *m/z* values. It is highly characteristic of the compound that no two compounds can have similar mass spectra. It provides information regarding the molecular structure of organic and inorganic compounds. Mass spectrum of Nd and Sm complexes are presented in Fig. 5(a)-(b). Assignment of neodymium complex; molecular formula of complex i.e. $(\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{S})_2\text{Nd}(\text{OH}_2)_4$, (Mol. wt. = 1107.34). In mass spectra of Nd complex a peak at *m/z* 1109.24 is due to the molecular mass of the complex i.e. $(\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{S})_2\text{Nd}(\text{OH}_2)_4$ or $(\text{ML}_2)^{+}$, peak at *m/z* 380.22 due to $[\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_5\text{O}_5\text{S}]^{+}$ ions, *m/z* 323.16 due to $[\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3\text{S}]^{+}$ ions base peak ion 90% relative abundance, *m/z* 229.14 due to $[\text{C}_9\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}]^{+}$, *m/z* 172.02

Fig. 4. NMR spectra of GLP and its Nd and Sm complexes.

due to $[C_7H_8NO_2S]^+$, m/z 132.06 due to $[C_8H_{12}N_2]^+$ radical ions.

Assignment of samarium complex, molecular formula of complex i.e. $(C_{21}H_{26}N_5O_4S)_2Sm(OH_2)_4$, (Mol. wt. =

1113.15). In mass spectra of Sm complex a peak at m/z 1112.08 is due to the molecular mass of the complex i.e. $(C_{21}H_{26}N_5O_4S)_2Sm(OH_2)_4$ or $(ML_2)^+$, peak at m/z 375.12 due to $[C_{15}H_{16}N_5O_5S]^+$ ions, peak at m/z 321.07

Fig. 5. Mass spectra of Nd and Sm complexes.

due to $[C_{14}H_{15}N_4O_3S]^+$ ions base peak ion 90% relative abundance, m/z 226.02 due to $[C_9H_{12}N_2O_3S]^+$, m/z 168.27 due to $[C_7H_8NO_2S]^+$, m/z 135.10 due to $[C_8H_{12}N_2]^+$ radical ions.

X-Ray diffraction studies :

The X-ray diffraction pattern for Nd and Sm complexes is shown in Fig. 6(a)-(b). It can be seen from the

figures that the main characteristic scattering peaks for GLP-Nd are at 11° , 16° , 18° , 22° and 24° while for GLP-Sm these peaks are found to be at 15° , 29° , 40° and 50° positions which indicated that the complex formed is a well knit one^{35,36}. The crystallographic data for Nd and Sm complexes are listed in Table 3. From the crystallographic data, unit cell parameters are obtained for

Fig. 6. X-Ray diffraction pattern for GLP-Nd and GLP-Sm complexes.

Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} complexes which attributed to monoclinic crystal system. The particle size is calculated from X-ray line broadening using the Scherrer formula $D_{hkl} = \kappa\lambda/\beta_{hkl} \cos \theta$, where D is the particle diameter in angstroms, κ is a coefficient and is equal to 0.89 here, β is the half-maximum line width, and λ is the wavelength of

X-rays. Space group for these complexes is Pmmm and interfacial angles are $\alpha = 90^\circ$, $\beta = 90^\circ$ and $\gamma = 89.78^\circ$.

Thermal analyses (TGA) :

The TGA curve for the Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} complexes are presented in Fig. 7(a)-(b). $(C_{21}H_{26}N_5O_4S)_2Nd(OH_2)_4$ complex is thermally decomposed in three decomposition

Table 2. IR spectra of the Nd and Sm complexes

Ligand/Complex	$\nu(NH)$	$\nu(S=O)$	$\nu(C=O)$	$\nu(SO_2N)$	$\nu(C=N)$	$\nu(M-O)$	$\nu(H_2O)$
$C_{21}H_{27}N_5O_4S$	3352	1216	1668	1325	1645	-	-
$(C_{21}H_{26}N_5O_4S)_2Nd(OH_2)_4$	3327	1218	-	1352	1602	463	3625
$(C_{21}H_{26}N_5O_4S)_2Sm(OH_2)_4$	3381	-	-	1353	1627	483	3606

Table 3. Crystallographic data of Nd and Sm complexes

Complex	Crystal system	Space group	Volume (Å ³)	Porosity (%)	Density (g cm ⁻³)	Particle size (µm)
$(C_{21}H_{26}N_5O_4S)_2Nd(OH_2)_4$	Monoclinic	Pmmm	14072.097	0.1708	0.0761	9.196
$(C_{21}H_{26}N_5O_4S)_2Sm(OH_2)_4$	Monoclinic	Pmmm	14065.752	0.0564	0.0765	9.418

Table 4. Kinetic parameters using the Freeman-Carroll and Sharp-Wentworth methods for Nd and Sm complexes

Compd.	Method	Parameter				
		E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG (kJ mol ⁻¹)	n
(C ₂₁ H ₂₆ N ₅ O ₄ S) ₂ Nd(OH ₂) ₄	FC	25.49	-197.48	2.519	61.763	0.85
	SW	20.67	-237.23	2.514	73.683	-
(C ₂₁ H ₂₆ N ₅ O ₄ S) ₂ Sm(OH ₂) ₄	FC	23.72	-199.51	2.517	62.370	0.83
	SW	17.90	-207.81	2.512	64.885	-

steps within in the temperature range of 50–600 °C. The first decomposition step with an estimated mass loss of 6.78 (Calcd. 6.50%) with in the temperature range 300–350 °C may be attributed to the liberation of the water molecules of hydration. The remaining decomposition steps found within the temperature from 350–400 °C and 400–510 °C might be due to organic moiety in Nd^{III} complex. The thermogram of (C₂₁H₂₆N₅O₄S)₂Sm(OH₂)₄ chelate

shows two decomposition steps within the temperature range from 50–600 °C. The first step within the temperature range from 350–400 °C may account for the loss of water molecules of hydration with a mass loss of 6.98% (Calcd. 6.46%). The subsequent step (400–510 °C) corresponds to the removal of metal oxide as a residue.

Kinetics studies :

The Freeman-Carroll³⁷ and Sharp-Wentworth³⁸ meth-

Fig. 7. TGA curves of GLP-Nd and GLP-Sm complexes.

ods have been employed for the calculation of kinetic parameters of the newly synthesized complexes with help of dynamic TG curve.

Fig. 8. FC kinetic plot of GLP-Nd and GLP-Sm complexes.

Freeman-Carroll method :

In this method, activation energy and order of reaction are related to following equation as;

$$\frac{\Delta \log \frac{dw}{dt}}{\Delta \log Wr} = n - \frac{E_a}{2.303R} \cdot \frac{\Delta \frac{1}{T}}{\Delta \log Wr} \quad (1)$$

where, $\frac{dw}{dt}$ = rate of change of weight with time and $Wr = Wc - W$, $Wc = Wt$. loss at completion of reaction, $W =$ Total wt. loss up to time 't', $E_a =$ energy of activation, $n =$ order of reaction. The plot of the term $\frac{\Delta \log \frac{dw}{dt}}{\Delta \log Wr}$ vs $\frac{\Delta \frac{1}{T}}{\Delta \log Wr}$ is a straight line with a slope of

$(-E_a/2.303R)$ (Fig. 8(a)-(b)). Energy of activation (E_a) is determined from the slope and order of reaction (n) obtained with the help of intercept.

Sharp-Wentworth method :

In this method E_a can be evaluated by the following expression;

$$\frac{\Delta \log \frac{dc}{dT}}{(1-c)} = \log \frac{A}{B} - \frac{E_a}{2.303R} \cdot \frac{1}{T} \quad (2)$$

where, $\frac{dc}{dT}$ = rate of change of fraction of weight with change in temperature. Fig. 9(a)-(b) shows a plot of the left-hand side of eq. (2) against $1/T$ gives a slope from which E_a was calculated. The entropy (ΔS), enthalpy (ΔH) and the free energy change (ΔG) were calculated using the following equations;

$$\Delta S = \left[\frac{\ln t}{1} - \frac{\log kR}{h\phi E_a} \right] \times 2.303 \times R \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta H = E_a - RT \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S \quad (5)$$

The calculated values of kinetic parameters such as energy of activation (E_a), enthalpy (ΔH), entropy (ΔS) and free energy change (ΔG) are given in Table 4. According to the kinetic data Nd and Sm complexes have negative values of entropy, which indicate that complexes have more ordered systems³⁹.

Conclusion

For supporting the proposed structure of Nd and Sm complexes with "GLP" initially Job's method of continuous variation as modified by Turner and Anderson was conducted which indicate 2 : 1 ligand : metal ratio of the complexes, moreover stability constant and free energy change were also calculated from modified Job's method. As a next step the synthesized complexes were isolated in pure powder form. Analytical data agree to the molecular formulae of the complexes. Molar conductance values support the non ionic nature of the complexes. The tentative structure assigned to the complexes on the basis of analytical data was further supported by modern spectroscopic methods like IR, ¹H NMR and Mass spectral studies etc. From IR spectra, it is revealed that the number of

Fig. 9. SW kinetic plot of GLP-Nd and GLP-Sm complexes.

frequencies and peaks which were present in ligand molecule gets modified in complexes and some new frequencies appeared which are fully supporting the proposed structure of the complexes. The presence of coordinated water and the symmetry of the complexes appeared to be hexagonal. In mass spectra of Nd and Sm complexes the base peak of the ligand appear on m/z 321.14 while short peak of the complexes appear on m/z 1115.08 for Nd and m/z 1120.14 for Sm complexes is quite supportive. A detail study of X-ray also supports the complex formation and various parameters were evaluated. TGA analysis has been studied by giving their relative thermal stability, applying the Freeman-Carroll and Sharp-Wentworth methods and result shows that the kinetic parameters (E_a , ΔH , ΔS and ΔG) evaluated by both methods are in a very good agreement.

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